

SHORT COMMUNICATIONS

Cyanogen Compounds of Pentavalent Rhenium

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In previous communications^{1,2}, studies on the acid association of $[\text{ReO}_5(\text{CN})_4]^{3-}$ and the properties of a cyano acid $\text{H}[\text{ReO}(\text{OH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{CN})_3]$ (A) were reported. Further studies on these cyano complexes of pentavalent rhenium are presented below.

The violet colour obtained by addition of acid to a solution of $\text{K}_3[\text{ReO}_5(\text{CN})_4]$ was shown³ by Job's method of continued variation to be a 1:1 complex between $[\text{ReO}_5(\text{CN})_4]^{3-}$ and H^+ . The intensity of the colour increases with time due to the transformation $\text{H}[\text{ReO}_5(\text{CN})_4]^{3-} \rightarrow [\text{ReO}(\text{OH})(\text{CN})_4]^{2-}$. The kinetics of the reaction

has been studied spectrophotometrically and the reaction found to be a second order one with velocity constant 0.019 lit. mole⁻¹ sec⁻¹ at 28°.

The soluble acid (A) loses water on long standing and the crystals tend to disintegrate spontaneously on exposure to atmosphere. In TGA of the substance first loss in weight began at 70° and continued upto 130° after which the loss was very steep and a nearly horizontal appeared at 340°. The loss in weight upto 130° was 3.0% and the total loss at 340° was 17.6%. On keeping a freshly prepared sample of the acid in vacuum over P_2O_5 , it lost 2.8% in weight which corresponds to the loss of half a molecule of water. The residue was pink and insoluble in water and in common organic solvents. The analysis of the insoluble substance corresponded to

The I.R. spectra of the soluble acid (A) gave characteristic OH, CN and H_2O frequencies at 3200(ah), 2170(s) and 1650(ah) cm^{-1} respectively and further bands at 1110(w), 1070(w), 1030(m), 952(m) and 922(m) cm^{-1} in the $\text{Re}=\text{O}$ and $\text{Re}-\text{O}-\text{H}$ region. The I.R. spectra of the insoluble polymer acid (B) was essentially the same.

On heating a freshly prepared sample of the soluble acid (A) at 300°, a constant weight stage was obtained after a loss of 17.5%, compared to the loss of 17.6% in TGA at 340°.

1. M. C. Chakravorti, *this Journal*, 1964, 41, 477.
2. *Idem, ibid*, 1966, 43, 381.

